

How To Comply With Local Law 87 New York City?

All buildings over 50,000 gross square feet in New York City must undertake periodic energy audits and retro-commissioning steps, according to Local Law 87 (LL87). It is in line with the Plan for Greener, Bigger Buildings (GGBP).

The purpose of this regulation is to provide building owners with information about their energy usage through energy audits, which survey and evaluate energy use, and retro-commissioning, which guarantees proper equipment installation and operation.

The following are examples of duties that fall under NYC LL87:

- It is identifying whether or not a structure must conform, as well as the deadline.
- Conduct an energy audit and retro-commissioning of base building systems and complete an electronic Energy Efficiency Report (EER).

The EER must be submitted to the city every ten years.

The following items are in the retro-commissioning data:

- Information about team building in general.
- Inventory of available equipment.
- Dissection of Energy and Use.
- The audit led to the discovery of energy-saving measures.
- Measures to bring a building back into service once it has decommissioned.

Local law 87 requirements.

- All structures with a total area of more than 50,000 square feet or multiple systems on a single property with a total area of more than 100,000 square feet.
- An Energy Efficiency Report must be completed and submitted (EER).
- Every ten years, buildings are required to submit an audit and retro commission.
- The last digit of your last block number determines the year you must comply.

Local law 87 extension.

Suppose the building cannot complete the energy audit and retro-commissioning due to reasonable faith efforts, time extensions for Local Law 87. If the building is experiencing financial difficulties, it may be eligible for an extension. LL87 requires a \$155 extension request.

The following are the rules for financial difficulty under Local Law 87:

- Has property taxes in arrears for at least two years before filing an EER on the Department of Finance's annual New York City tax lien auction list.
- Is exempt from real property taxes under absolute property tax sections 420-a, 420-b, 446, or 462 of the law.
- Has unpaid sums under the Department of [nyc local law 97](#) Housing Preservation and Development's Emergency Repair Program, which resulted in the property included on the Department of

Finance's annual New York city tax sale list less than two years before filing the EER. - The Department of Buildings must receive payments via mail. It costs \$375 to file a complaint. It costs \$145 to make an amendment. - Make sure you save your documents! Failure to comply with Local Law 87 will result in a punishment of \$3000 the first year and \$5,000 each year after that. - The implementation of recommendations is not required by Local Law 87. - Keep records for 11 years after the due date.

Conclusion

The NYC Retrofit Accelerator is another excellent resource. The City of New York launched the accelerator to assist building owners in lowering operating expenses and increasing sustainability. The accelerator provides free, individualized services that connect you with suitable contractors and assist you in locating incentives and funding to help pay for repairs.